

THE NEED FOR AN AIR FORCE ELECTROSTATIC DISCHARGE
CONTROL PROGRAM: A STRATEGIC PLANNING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This paper conveys the need for an effective Air Force electrostatic discharge (ESD) control program. As technology decreases the size of electronic components, it simultaneously increases the susceptibility of those components to ESD. These discharges of electrical energy between two bodies occur continuously in any work environment and can cause significant problems when working on electronic equipment. The Air Force attempts to overcome numerical advantages of its potential adversaries through the use of sophisticated technologies, especially in the area of electronics. Consequently, as the Air Force increases the use of sophisticated electronic technology, it simultaneously increases the susceptibility of its avionics to ESD and the need for an Air Force ESD control program. The author examines studies done by others in the field of research, both within and outside the Air Force, that show the Air Force does have an ESD problem. These studies also show the return on investment for implementing a control program can be as much as 2300 percent and can save the Air Force hundreds of millions of dollars per year. The paper closes with a proposal for a strategic planning approach the Air Force can take.

WHAT'S THE PROBLEM?

It is a law of nature that when any two substances (solids, liquids, or gasses) come together and then come apart (even a hand passing through air), an exchange of electrons between the two substances will occur. As a result, one object will have a net gain of electrons and the other a loss. The item that gains electrons will become negatively charged while the other becomes positively charged. This is called an electrostatic charge.

All objects will carry this charge until it can be neutralized. When two objects of dissimilar charges come close enough to each other such that the voltage between them is greater than the breakdown voltage of the medium separating the items, an electrical current will flow in an attempt to equalize the charge between them. These discharges of electrostatic energy between two bodies are called electrostatic discharges (ESD).

An excellent example of the ESD phenomenon is when you receive a spark from a doorknob after walking across the carpet on a dry winter day.

The fact that you feel the spark means that it is at least 2500 volts, since that is approximately the threshold for human sensitivity to an ESD. Studies have shown that the spark described above can be as much as 35,000 volts.

All items are susceptible to being destroyed by an excess transfer of electrical charge. Lightning, an extremely powerful form of ESD, can turn a bag of sand to glass. A human being can be killed by putting a finger in a light socket. The use of too many kitchen appliances at one time can blow a fuse.

As technology decreases the size of electronic components, it simultaneously increases the susceptibility of those components to ESD. Their small size makes them more easily destroyed by smaller amounts of electricity, sometimes by less than 50 volts. Electrostatic discharges occur continuously in any work environment and can cause significant damage to electronic equipment.

One study showed that the damage caused by an ESD can be a hole measuring 6 microns across. With today's integrated circuit technology reducing device features to 0.5 microns, a hole of this size could "swallow up" several complete transistors.

From the discussion above, we see that the environment generates many electrostatic discharges, some very large, and that electronic equipment in use today is extremely susceptible to ESD. Many times, when an ESD damages a piece of equipment, we won't even feel the ESD when it occurs. Therefore, damaged equipment may be placed in service, with potentially devastating results. Thus, ESD control must be a priority for any organization that relies on using state-of-the-art electronic equipment.

The Air Force relies on sophisticated electronic equipment to help it overcome the numerical advantage our potential adversaries have. This "force multiplier" equipment uses highly advanced, state-of-the-art electronic components that are extremely miniaturized, resulting in equipment that uses fewer resources (weight, fuel, power, and cooling). As a result, the Air Force gets more capability at a lower cost.

The tradeoff for the Air Force's increasing use of sophisticated electronics that use smaller components is the simultaneous increase of the susceptibility of its avionics to ESD. The Air Force's need for an effective ESD control program to reduce the damage caused by ESD when handling electronic equipment increases every time we

"shrink" our electronic components.

DOES THE PROBLEM REALLY EXIST?

In a paper by G. I. Dangelmeyer of the Western Electric Company, the author reports "a technique which has proven successful in estimating the benefit of ESD precautions and subsequently establishing a systematic and cost-effective prevention plan." His experimental data showed improvements ranging from 1.9:1 (number of defects with no ESD precautions to number of defects with ESD precautions) to 5.5:1. In one case, the return on investment was 950%.

In a report by Donald Frank of the Douglas Aircraft Company, the author concludes "that only a relatively small portion of ESD damage resulted in hard or reported failures." New technology systems were having "three to four times as many soft failures and data discrepancies." "Failure analysis revealed that more than one-third of these soft failures were due to component degradation resulting from electrostatic discharge" and "that 80 to 90 percent of the ESD damage was not hard failure, but 'wounds'." These "walking wounded" still worked well enough to pass acceptance-tests, but were not fully capable of working in the full range they were designed for. Right now, it is estimated that over 60 percent of the components in avionics are sensitive to electrostatic discharges of less than 100 volts and that "there is absolutely no activity that can be performed (even the simple act of raising an arm) that will not generate more than 100 volts."

A report by Owen McAteer shows that latent failures due to ESD do exist, and that they cause lower equipment reliability. The report further concluded that the customer is particularly vulnerable to them.

Texas Instruments performed a study and reduced ESD failures by 247 percent in the first year and 350 percent in the first nine months of the second year (when the paper was published).

W. Y. McFarland studied the economic benefits of implementing an effective ESD control program. The return on investment of the Western Electric Company program was found to be 2300 percent. Melvin Downing reports that the Lockheed Missiles and Space Company spent \$185.1 thousand to implement an ESD control program and \$45 thousand per year to operate it. The savings, however, ranged from \$1.615 million the first year and increased to \$1.8 million in the fourth year.

The relevance of ESD controls to the Air Force was discussed in several reports done by the Air Force Materials Laboratory which showed as much as two-thirds of failed devices were damaged by ESD. The Aerospace Guidance and Metrology Center (AGMC) received a payback of 3.5 to 1 for implementing a model ESD control program. They also found that repair costs decreased by 30 percent and the number of parts repaired increased by 45 percent. Some estimates are that as much as 50 percent of Air Force avionics failures

are due to ESD. Fixing these failures could easily cost hundreds of millions of dollars per year. Other estimates are that approximately 30 percent of the ESD failures occur in the field, which means that the end user must also take precautions. An ESD control program would improve reliability by reducing failure rates and improve maintainability by reducing maintenance times.

Downing succinctly points out that the lack of proof of ESD damage has often caused a reluctance by management to fund any corrective programs. Frank points out that the damage wrought by ESD can be ten times more encompassing than we may realize, due to the hidden nature of most of the failures. Now is the time for Air Force management to realize that ESD damage exists, to larger extents than we realize, and the costs of implementing a control program will be more than paid for by the resulting savings.

WHAT WILL SOLVING THE PROBLEM RESULT IN?

The solution to the Air Force ESD problem must include the following:

1. It must reduce the number of parts failing due to ESD.
2. It must apply to all people that work with Air Force ESD sensitive items. This includes contracting, developing, supply, transportation, and maintenance personnel, at every echelon of involvement, from headquarters to field units.
3. It must include a policy statement to describe applicability, assign responsibility, and ensure adherence to the program.
4. It must provide a feedback mechanism to determine the effectiveness of the program.
5. It must make the appropriate information available to the individuals responsible for implementing the program.
6. It must provide a means for implementers to ask questions and get suitable answers.
7. It must provide a methodology for making and assessing technical solutions.

WHAT ARE OUR CHOICES?

Before enumerating possible alternative solutions, we should state the obvious: the fundamental criteria for choosing a solution is that it must ultimately result in more of something (utils, peace of mind, combat capability, etc) per unit of resources used (money, people, time, etc). This is the "more bang per buck" issue. Any action taken should either result in a higher ratio of defense to cost, or it should not be taken. The only exception to this would be in cases where the fundamental problem is an insufficient number of utils (e.g., combat capability) to meet an absolute minimum objective (e.g., winning a war). There is a minimum level of defense a country must maintain in order to survive. Also, in defense there are

limited resources available to pay any increased costs, so that actions can sometimes not be taken even if the increase in benefits exceeds the costs (i.e., there just aren't enough dollars in the budget to always be able to pay for all beneficial things). The bottom line is that the Air Force must be able to defend the U.S. adequately and in a cost effective manner. However, determining the minimum level of defense is well beyond the scope of this paper. Our criteria will only be to increase our benefits received per dollar spent.

One alternative, obviously, is to do nothing. Perhaps the Air Force really doesn't have an ESD problem or we can easily determine that solving the problem would use up more resources than it would save. We ask ourselves the question "Can the Air Force provide more defense per dollar spent by adopting better ESD controls?" and the answer is "No." If either of these were true, then we could simply stop here. But the evidence discussed earlier shows that it looks as if an Air Force ESD problem does exist and the savings derived from implementing an ESD control program would more than pay for the cost of the program.

Another obvious alternative is to study the problem some more. We could collect more data to specifically see if there truly is an Air Force ESD problem and how extensive it is. At least this alternative has the positive attribute of providing a structured research program to undisputably find these things out. Meanwhile, assuming the study proved an extensive Air Force problem does exist, this option would allow the ESD problem to continue wasting resources. So why restudy a problem that has already been extensively studied? Furthermore, to do a proper cost-benefit analysis, a study would have to measure the costs of implementing an ESD control program with the resulting benefits (i.e., the reduction in ESD damage). These data could only be reliably estimated by implementing a carefully controlled pilot program, sufficiently large to statistically represent the entire Air Force.

The third alternative is to adopt an integrated Air Force ESD control program. Continued study of the problem might only lead to proving "the sun rises in the east" (a proof of the already obvious). The studies previously discussed show that a proper ESD control program is extremely cost effective. This alternative would take the existing ESD control program, such as it exists, and broaden and strengthen it. It would have to provide better policy and guidance, designate implementing organizations, and make available the resources to execute the program. The cornerstone and initial action to take would be to formulate a strong and effective Air Force-wide policy.

One choice is to put the policy in a DOD standard (DOD-STD) or DOD handbook (DOD-HDBK). A STD and HDBK covering ESD controls already exist. The problems with them are the limited availability and the difficulty of revising them. STDs and HDBKs are not documents widely distributed throughout the Air Force. Ask a crew chief where

a copy of DOD-STD-1686 or DOD-HDBK-263 is and you'll probably get a blank stare. Furthermore, since these are DOD-wide documents that also affect contractors, the coordination of changes is an extremely lengthy process (often as long as several years). Also, these documents are not required to be followed unless they are contractually invoked or required by policy. The first page of DOD-HDBK-263 makes the statement that "these are not mandatory requirements." Finally, these types of documents are not recognized as sources of Air Force policy. Rather, they implement policy. Thus, this choice has some serious drawbacks.

Another choice is to put the policy in a technical order (TO). A TO on ESD controls already exists. However, it also is not an Air Force policy document. Rather, it is an operating level instruction. A TO provides specific "how to" procedures for users and maintenance personnel to follow. The current TO lacks sufficient guidance to allow quality assurance or inspection personnel to ensure that an effective ESD control program exists. It also lacks the breadth of coverage to ensure that ESD controls are in place throughout the chain of handling, from contractors to field units. For example, it does not apply to flight line or contractor personnel. Finally, a TO doesn't have a wide distribution. A crew chief will probably know where to find a TO, but mid and upper level management usually don't use these documents as sources of guidance in carrying out their jobs. Furthermore, Air Force Systems Command personnel rarely ever see a TO (usually only when doing TO Verification and Validation).

A third choice is to put the policy in an existing Air Force Regulation (AFR). AFR 800-18 has a short paragraph in it which merely states that an effective ESD control program will be implemented in accordance with DOD-STD-1686, DOD-HDBK-263, and TO 00-25-234, Section VII. Efforts to expand on this guidance failed. As a result, the only existing ESD control program policy is in a regulation that covers a different, although related subject. This makes the policy difficult to find (it actually hides it). It also subordinates the ESD policy to the other subject and makes it appear that the ESD policy is only required in conjunction with the other policy.

Finally, we can put the policy in a separate AFR. This choice allows for specific control of this policy. It doesn't subordinate or hide it. Regulations represent Air Force policy, whereas STDs, HDBKs, and TOs serve a different purpose. As a result, regulations are much more readily and widely available than a STD, HDBK, or TO. Ask the same crew chief, manager, or Systems Command person where a copy of an AFR is and they'll probably know. Additionally, regulations are used by quality assurance personnel and inspectors, whereas STDs, HDBKs, and TOs may not be. These personnel ensure compliance with policy. Thus it is important that the policy be in a document that they use. Finally, an Air Force regulation can be written to have general applicability to all personnel working with ESD sensitive equipment and at all levels of management. This contrasts with

other documents which have more limited applicability.

WHAT'S THE BEST SOLUTION?

The logical decision is to implement an effective Air Force ESD control program. In order to be effective, it must include feedback and control mechanisms which will ensure that the program is on track and truly does provide "more bang per buck." The feedback would provide hard data on the effectiveness (or ineffectiveness) of the program so that resources could be realigned as necessary.

Since the Air Force uses formal policy statements (regulations) to guide its activities, how that policy is formulated and carried out is very important to its successful implementation. If a policy is determined to be needed, it should go in a policy document (i.e., an AFR) and not be hidden in non-policy documents just to "reduce the proliferation of regulations." The magnitude of the problem a policy addresses should dictate the amount of visibility the policy receives. The magnitude of the ESD problem is bigger than the visibility the Air Force currently gives it. It deserves a separate regulation.

This is certainly an Air Force-wide problem that upper level management must get involved in. The current Air Force policy is a piecemeal approach that falls short of providing an effective ESD control program. To provide proper management attention and visibility, the optimum vehicle for an ESD control program policy is a separate Air Force Regulation.

HOW CAN WE IMPLEMENT AN ESD CONTROL PROGRAM?

Policy:

Headquarters U.S. Air Force (HQ USAF) needs to authorize a new AFR to provide Air Force policy for ESD control. It should establish, outline, and direct the Air Force ESD control program. It should establish the requirement to maintain a continuous chain of control of ESD sensitive items, from contractor to user, including all handling points such as supply, transportation, repair, and installation. Such a regulation should, at a minimum, require each major command (MAJCOM) headquarters to identify an office of primary responsibility (OPR), identify categories of ESD sensitive items, ensure minimum sensitivity in new item designs, provide guidance as to when to contractually invoke DOD-STD-1686, and provide guidance on training. A draft AFR was proposed to HQ USAF.

Organization:

To implement the policy, two organizations should be established, using existing resources. The first organization would be an Air Force ESD technology Center. It would combine the resources at the Rome Air Development Center (RADC) at Griffiss AFB in New York and the AGMC at Newark AFB in Ohio. RADC currently performs research

into developing new equipment designs that are ESD resistant. They look towards the future. AGMC specifies appropriate ESD control equipment and procedures to reduce ESD damage to current inventory. They look at the present. (AGMC does this via AFLCR 65-8 which designates it as the AFLC ESD Technology Center.) Although these two organizations are currently working the ESD problem, no charter exists to bring their efforts together and ensure that they are working towards a common goal.

The second organization needed is an Air Force ESD control program working group. It should consist of individuals from the Air Force ESD Technology Center and people involved in executing the ESD control program. This forum should periodically meet (once a year at least, more often, if necessary) to discuss the effectiveness of the program, assess strong and weak points, and make recommendations for improving it.

Resources:

The resources needed to implement an effective Air Force ESD control program include people to execute the program (most are already in place), training materials (parts of which already exist, e.g., films and manuals), and the actual ESD control equipment (wrist straps, mats, testers, ionizers, packing materials, etc) which is already available. Additional funding would be required to sponsor the organizations described above, and pay for travel, training, and the equipment. However, as previously discussed, these costs would be more than offset by a reduction in total Air Force Operations and Maintenance (O&M) costs.

Feedback:

To evaluate the effectiveness of the ESD control program, the Air Force Inspector General (IG) needs to evaluate unit or organizational adherence to the ESD policies, as outlined in the Air Force regulation described above. In particular, the IG should look for the following during their visits to Air Force units:

1. Do MAJCOM headquarters have a designated OPR tasked to develop and execute an effective ESD control program for their MAJCOM?
2. Has the OPR tailored Air Force policy and guidance to fit the needs of its command? Has it published in a command regulation or supplement to the AFR?
3. Has an effective ESD control program been initiated at subordinate units, including depot, intermediate, and flight line maintenance organizations? Does it include:
 - a. Training.
 - b. Appropriate use of ESD control equipment.
 - c. Proper marking of ESD sensitive items.

d. Quality surveillance by management and shop foremen to ensure compliance with Air Force and local policies and guidance, and to identify ESD control program deficiencies.

The Air Force IG is performing inspections for adequacy of the existing Air Force ESD control program. This is a Special Interest Item that they are looking at between January 1988 and June 1989.

Another method of evaluating the effectiveness of an Air Force ESD control program is to have the Air Force laboratories and Air Logistic Centers perform scanning electron microscope evaluations of failed ESD sensitive devices (e.g., integrated microcircuits). These failure analyses would provide information as to the exact cause of failure of the device. This information could be used to perform trend analyses to verify the effectiveness of an ESD control program.

SUMMARY

In summary, I've shown in this article that ESD is a problem inherent in our environment which the Air Force is not adequately addressing. The potential benefits of implementing an ESD control program far outweigh the costs. I have proposed that the Air Force publish ESD policy in a separate AFR and accord this problem the visibility it deserves.

References

1. U.S. Department of the Air Force: Air Force Reliability and Maintainability Policy. AFR 800-18. Washington D.C.: Government Printing Office, 1 Oct 1986.
2. U.S. Department of the Air Force. General Shop Practice Requirements for the Repair, Maintenance, and Test of Electronic Equipment. Technical Manual 00-25-234. Warner-Robins ALC (MMEDT), Robins AFB GA, 1 Apr 1983.
3. U.S. Department of Defense. Electrostatic Discharge Control Handbook for Protection of Electrical and Electronic Parts, Assemblies and Equipment (Excluding Electrically Initiated Explosive Devices). DOD-HDBK-263. Washington D.C.: Government Printing Office, 2 May 1980.
4. U.S. Department of Defense. Electrostatic Discharge Control Program for Protection of Electrical and Electronic Parts, Assemblies and Equipment (Excluding Electrically Initiated Explosive Devices). DOD-STD-1686. Washington D.C.: Government Printing Office, 2 May 1980.
5. Electrostatic Damage Control Efforts; An Expense or an Investment? A Businessman's Guide for Understanding, Developing, and Participating in Electrostatic Control Efforts. Chicago IL: ADE, Inc, 1981.
6. Abel, E., MSgt., USAF. "ESD Comes with the Territory," MSET Review, SACRP 66-2, Volume 21, Number 2. Headquarters Strategic Air Command, Offutt AFB NE, April-June 1986, pp. 2-4.
7. Danglemeier, G. T. "ESD - How Often Does it Happen," Electrical Overstress/Electrostatic Discharge Symposium Proceeding, 1983, pp. 1-5.
8. Dobbs, William. "Evaluation Report: Minuteman II Inertial Guidance Computer Parts," Dayton OH: U.S. Air Force, Air Force Wright Aeronautics Laboratories, Materials Laboratory, Systems Support Division, 3 April 1985 pp. 1-16.
9. Downing, M. H. "ESD Control Implementation and Cost Avoidance Analysis," Electrical Overstress/Electrostatic Discharge Symposium Proceeding, 1983, pp. 6-10.
10. Frank, Donald E. "The Perfect '10' - Can You Really Have One," Electrical Overstress/Electrostatic Discharge Symposium Proceeding, 1981, pp. 21-26.
11. McAleer, G. H., G. H. Lucas and A. McDonald. "A Pragmatic Approach to ESD Problem Solving in the Manufacturing Environment, A Case History," Electrical Overstress/Electrostatic Discharge Symposium Proceeding, 1981, pp. 34-39.
12. McAteer, Owen J., R. E. Twist and R. C. Walker. "Latent ESD Failures," Electrical Overstress/Electrostatic Discharge Symposium Proceeding, 1982, pp. 41-48.
13. McFarland, W. Y. "The Economic Benefits of an Effective Electrostatic Discharge Awareness and Control Program - An Empirical Analysis," Electrical Overstress/Electrostatic Discharge Symposium Proceeding, 1981, pp. 28-32.